

Fundamental of Theories on Human Resource Quality Improvement in the Universities and Lesson Learned For Svay Rieng University, Cambodia

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Human Resources, Quality Improvement, Lesson Learned, Svay Rieng University

Received : 3 December

Revised : 18 December

Accepted : 20 January

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ABSTRACT

The development of human resources in education and training is becoming more important, and the roles of human resources have become necessary to contribute to all sectors of national development. This study aims to codify the fundamental theories on human resources quality improvement in universities and draw lessons learned for Svay Rieng University. As a methodology, the research results are mainly collected from the published information, and descriptive statistics are the principal analytical method used in this article. The study presents the basic concepts of human resources, human resources quality, human resources management structure in universities, and the rational structure of human resources in universities. As lessons learned, in order to develop the quality of lecturers as well as human resources at Svay Rieng University, first of all, it must have proper, reasonable, and objective assessments so that it can clearly find out the strengths, weaknesses, and constraints of human resources quality improvement. After accurately assessing these issues, it is necessary to have regulations, policies, and strategies for human resources development; therefore, human resources can constantly improve their quality and quantity to meet the vision and mission of the university in the next period

INTRODUCTION

Humans are the goal and the driving force behind the development of all organizations, especially in education and training. The development of human resources (HR) is even becoming more important. To provide qualified education and training services in higher education institutions, the improvement of HR is necessarily needed, and it has been learned from some fundamental theories and practices from other institutions that have successfully achieved their vision and mission.

This study aims to codify the fundamental theories on human resources quality improvement in universities and draw lessons learned for Svay Rieng University (SRU).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Improving the quality of HR is a great topic that has drawn a lot of attention from scholars and researchers because the roles of HR have been necessary to contribute to all sectors of national development (Tran Van Hung, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

Since this is an overview study, the research results are mainly based on the published information collected from published materials such as scientific journals, books, statistics, newspapers, and online documents. Descriptive statistics are the principal analytical method used in this article to reflect the concepts of human resources quality improvement from the other theories and practices and to provide lessons for the quality improvement of human resources at SRU, Cambodia.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Definition of Human Resources Quality Improvement

In general, human resources quality improvement (HRQI) is the improvement of the strength and creative capability of humans, both in physical and mental improvement, up to the highest level, and then those humans can be able to be involved in activities of socio-economic development in the developing period. HRQI includes the forms, methods, policies, and solutions to fulfill and improve the quality of labor (intellectual, physical, and psychological aspects) to meet the needs of HR for socio-economic development in each period of development (Matthew, 2006).

Objectives of Human Resources Quality Improvement

The overall objective of HRQI is to maximize the use of existing HR and improve the efficiency of institutions by helping staff better understand their work, mastery, functions, and duties. HRQI has certain effects and implications for both institutions and staff (Ha Van Hoi, 2013):

For Institutions:

1. Help institutions increase productivity and efficiency of works and services, and to create competitive advantages for institution.

2. Avoid outdated management: managers need to adopt management approaches that are appropriate for changes in technology, policy, and administrative processes.
3. Solve organizational problems: training and development can help the head of institution address conflicting issues, including conflicts between individuals, within institution and the head of institution, and to develop of HR management policies effectively.
4. Job guide for new staff and lecturers: new staff and lecturers often face many difficulties during the early days of working in organizations and institutions, therefore, job orientation programs will be needed for new staff and lecturers to help them quickly adapt to the new working environment.
5. Prepare the contingent of the head of institution and senior staff: training and development enable staff and lecturers to acquire the skills they need for advancement and to replace the head of institution and senior staff when necessary.

For Staff:

- Create professionalism and cohesion between staff, lecturers and institutions
- Help staff and lecturers directly perform better, especially when they perform jobs that do not meet the standard criteria, or when they transfer to the new career.
- Update new skills and knowledge for staff and lecturers to help them successfully apply technology changes and technique used in the institution.
- Meet the needs and aspirations of the staff and lecturers by equipping with the requisite professional skills that will motivate them to do better, to achieve better results, to be more challenging and to have more promotion opportunities.
- Give staff and lecturers a new way of thinking and thinking skills in their work which is also the basis for promoting creativity in the workplace.

Contents of Human Resources Quality Improvement

A. Physical Improvement

Physical improvement focuses on the health improvement of HR. Health is the important purpose of development, and it is also the condition of development. Health is the development of human harmony, both physical and mental. The health of the faculty staff and lecturers is influenced by a number of factors, such as natural, economic, and social factors, and is reflected by a set of indicators, including basic indicators of health, diseases, and health care conditions. In order to improve the quality of social services, it is necessary to improve the teaching fees, social justice, working environment, physical sports, and appropriate conditions for faculty staff, along with the provision of medical care services, a malnutrition program, and pregnant care for women (Trinh Duy Luan, 2002).

B. Mental Improvement

Mental improvement is focusing on the professional development of the capabilities of HR, such as knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behavior. It can be said that mental improvement means improving professional skills and knowledge for a career. Developing professional qualifications is very important for improving productivity, quality, and efficiency. Knowledge enhancement is the core element of HR development, and it can be done in a variety of forms, mostly through training and short course preparation (Tran Van Hung, 2016).

C. Spiritual Improvement

Spiritual improvement is focusing on raising awareness and professional ethics in HR, especially among faculty staff and lecturers. On professional ethics: enthusiasm for the profession, the sense of preservation of honor, the conscience of lecturers, the spirit of solidarity and love that actually help colleagues in life and work, tolerance, gentle treatment with students, colleagues, and the community. On living style: life with an ideal purpose is to overcome difficulties, to strive with pure motivation and creative thinking, and to be thrifty, honest, and carefree in work. Spiritual improvement is to work agilely, urgently, politely, with a scientific manner and a civilized attitude in social relations, with good communication with colleagues, and outside the institution. This improvement focuses on working together, helping colleagues accomplish tasks well, and fighting to prevent violations of law and professional regulations. This impacts relationships, right treatment, and closeness to people, parents, students, and learners. This improvement is also committed to building up a family of cultures, to love one another, to respect each other, to care for the people around, and to cultivate civilized culture in public. To protect and preserve the moral ethics of teachers, they must not abuse their positions and powers to commit acts of violating laws, regulations, or rules and do not cause trouble for learners or the public. There should be no fraud, dishonesty in work, scientific research, or implementation of teaching and education (Tran Van Hung, 2016).

Actions to Improve the Quality of Human Resources

A. Human Resources Planning

Human resource planning is the process of forecasting, researching, and identifying the human resource needs of an institution with the purpose of developing policies and action plans for the future to ensure sufficient human resources. Planning helps institutions develop the appropriate qualities and skills to process their work and achieve their vision. HRQI must have a strategic vision closely linked to the clear development planning of the institution. Its ultimate goal is to improve productivity and achieve organizational vision and mission. In order to ensure the highest quality of HR, we need to plan in detail and be clear. Human resource planning is the basis for activities to improve the quality of HR, contributing to smooth coordination in the implementation cycle. Human resource planning allows you to see how the parts work together and, at the same time, see the purpose of HRQI, whether the human resources are appropriate to the strategy, and ensure long-term competitive advantages (Trinh Duy Luan, 2002).

B. Recruitment, Use and Evaluation

Personnel recruitment is the process of finding and selecting faculty staff and lecturers to meet the needs of the institution and adding the workforce needed to accomplish the institution's vision. In other words, recruiting is the process of providing a special input to the organization, which is the human factor. The process consists of two main stages: attraction, search, and selection. These two stages have a close relationship with each other. If the staff and lecturers are of good quality, they can recruit qualified personnel and also increase the prestige of the recruitment process. To attract and find talented people to improve the

quality of the human resources of the institution. Recruitment is a very important factor in the HRQI of each organization. If recruiting works well, it should recruit qualified people with good qualifications. Conversely, if the recruitment is not well paid attention to, it will not be able to choose the virtuous people to work. The recruitment should be based on the principle of the needs of the job to recruit, be clear, objective, and fair. The recruitment must be done on the basis of determining the number of recruits, in which case it is necessary to analyze the position and work to set the conditions and criteria when recruiting (Tran Van Hung, 2016).

HR must follow the principle when setting the conditions and criteria for recruitment for any position because the placement of human resources into positions should be in line with the level of training and ability of each person towards specialization. The institution would create favorable conditions for them to develop their strengths and qualified capacity and contribute to the development of the organization.

Evaluation of work is an integral part of human resource management. It plays an important role in encouraging staff and lecturers to work better because the internal evaluation helps the organization treat staff equally and accountably. Staff and lecturers can see their achievements, motivation at work, and improved behavior in the direction of better. Most institutions have built their own performance evaluation system to assess the performance of their staff. Small universities evaluate their work informally through the daily assessment from the management board, the dean, and the mutual evaluation of the evaluators. Large universities are evaluating faculty staff and lecturers through advanced methods such as applying the Key Performance Indicator (KPI), developing clear job performance assessments, and receiving direct feedback from the manager (Trinh Duy Luan, 2002).

C. Remuneration Policy

Remuneration is the process of taking care of the material and spiritual lives of the staff so that they can fulfill their assigned tasks and thus contribute to fulfilling the goals and vision of the university. The human remuneration policy is implemented in two basic forms: financial remuneration and non-financial remuneration. Financial remuneration in the university is a form of remuneration provided by financial instruments, including various types such as wages, bonuses, allowances, grants, shares, etc. Non-financial remuneration is done through two types of treatment: work-based remuneration and work-environment remuneration, in order to meet the increasing spiritual needs of the working class, such as joy in life, excitement, passion for work, being treated fairly, respected, and being well communicated with (Trinh Duy Luan, 2002).

D. Human Resources Training

Human resource management is the most important criteria in the assessment of human resource quality. Knowledge is represented by the degree of education, professional knowledge, and professional capability of those human resources. Therefore, in order to improve human resources quality, institutions must regularly implement training programs and retraining courses for HR. Training and improving the professional level of faculty staff will ensure that HR at the

university can adapt to and follow the evolution and development of technology and use technology effectively to help the university successfully complete its goals. In the education environment, human resources, especially faculty staff and lecturers, are a very overwhelming resource, affirming the position of the university in the market. These are the talents of staff expressed by their skills in research and production to meet the increasing demands of society and the advancement of science, as well as to effectively produce the next generation of human resources (Trinh Duy Luan, 2002).

In addition, training and retraining also help staff improve their level of culture, expand their knowledge, and upgrade their quality. At the same time, taking care of their own health should be well taken care of for a positive attitude in labor, contributing to the improvement of human resources in institutions.

Factors Impacting The Quality Of Human Resources

A. Internal Factors

- The Policy of the School is to Invest in Improving the Quality of Human Resources in Universities

Improving the quality of human resources at schools is always a top priority. By educational institutions, qualified teachers and good employees have the opportunity to improve their position. Universities nationwide are always alarmed about the quality of their human resources, and they must have qualified and capable people to achieve their goals. The right policy of the school for improving the quality of human resources will bring a spirit of continuous learning and rise of cadres. They will try to improve their level, bring practical effects to the training of the school, attract students and gradually improve the position of the school in training. If the school does not pay attention to this work will be backward, stay behind. The faculty and staff in the school will not try to improve themselves, no sense of trying to strive to bring the school positive factors. School policies and policies play a vital role in determining the success of human resource development, as this is a long process and requires a consensus between the home with faculty and staff (Ha Van Hoi, 2013).

- Strategy to improve the quality of human resources in universities

Schools, if only policies and guidelines but not accompanied by strategies to improve the quality of human resources, this work will not achieve the desired effect. School strategies must be periodic, concrete, and specific. These strategies must be met in terms of content and effectiveness. Universities also devise specific strategies that are effective in improving the quality of human resources. School leaders or administrators must develop specific strategies for each stage of school development and evaluate the effectiveness of their strategies in order to obtain solutions. for the later periods of development of the school (Ha Van Hoi, 2013).

- Training of faculty and staff in universities

In current universities, the training of faculty and staff is always carried out along with setting criteria to help them achieve their goals and directions. At present, the training for cadres easily leads to the situation they achieve the things that the school set out but the quality of life reduced due to the care of many things, not enough funds to cover the funds. This leads to a lack of enthusiasm at work. The training for faculty and staff in the university must be comprehensive that in

the process of building and development of the school must be synchronized between the fostering to improve the level with the planning. The planning will help the management team to a certain period of time will determine whether the work of improving the quality of human resources being implemented is effective? Schools need to match their solutions with specific criteria that can bring the best conditions for staff to actively improve their capacity. Therefore, in the work of improving the quality of human resources must be comprehensive and so as to bring specific results bring positive impact for teachers and staff of the school (Ha Van Hoi, 2013).

B. External Factors

- International Cooperation, Development of Teaching Resources in Universities
International cooperation is a core issue in the development and linkage training of the school. Today, international cooperation offers a new opportunity for affiliate training and education. The programs that international cooperation brings are often high-quality programs from abroad. These programs are very diverse and there are many professions in economics, commerce, etc. Universities in recent years have promoted the linking of international cooperation. This linkage can be between universities through some of the world's leading universities. Together with the linkage, the improvement of the quality of human resources must also be invested, promoted. When defining international training cooperation, each school should prepare its mind and determine the goals that need to be achieved in international cooperation. In order to avoid the high cost of international cooperation and training that is costly, the school also needs to improve the quality of its faculty and staff. Therefore, international cooperation is an opportunity but also a challenge for any university, so that this program is really effective, the school should have a specific direction and plan in terms of cost, quality team (Ha Van Hoi, 2013).

- Government Policies for Improving the Quality of Human Resources

Throughout its development, the State has always paid much attention to building and fostering the quality of human resources. The policies provided to employees in different sectors of the economy towards the goals that need to be achieved in the work. Every year, the commendation ceremony is organized by the state to commend individuals and groups who have achieved high achievements and achieved great results in their work. Bring practical effects to society. Moreover, due to the state's emphasis on improving the quality of human resources, cadres working in state or private institutions are selected to study abroad. When you come home to contribute your efforts and what you have learned to devote to your home country. This is one of the directions for the state to develop and improve the quality of human resources has brought practical effects (Ha Van Hoi, 2013).

- Lessons Learned of Human Resources Quality Improvement for SRU

Cambodian universities have had practical development and experience for many years. The issue of improving the quality of human resources has always been highly appreciated by schools, bringing significant achievements and results to the school from improving the quality of human resources.

SRU is aware of the problem of improving the quality of human resources and needs a lot of time and enthusiasm. Therefore, to do well, this school must have specific goals and strategies for each period and stage. In these times, the school must evaluate the results achieved and have solutions and plans for the next period. Because not all schools are successful in improving the quality of human resources, the SRU recognizes and draws on the experience of well-known universities. Investing in improving the quality of human resources should be implemented effectively.

In the realities of SRU, it is recognized that to improve the quality of human resources, other work must also be done by the school. The work of ensuring the stability of the material and spiritual life for the teaching staff and staff must also be completed.

Therefore, if the school wants to improve the quality of its human resources to achieve certain effects, it must coordinate well with the above solutions to complete this work and achieve certain effects. for the staff of the school.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In order to develop the contingent of lecturers, first of all, it must have proper, reasonable, and objective assessments so that the strengths and weaknesses of the contingent of lecturers and their achievements can be clearly seen. as a constraint in development work. After accurately assessing these issues, it is necessary to have regulations and policies on staff planning, training, and fostering so that lecturers can constantly improve their quality and quantity. The amount meets the goals of the school in the new period.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Fundamental of Theories on Human Resource Quality Improvement in the Universities and Lesson Learned For Svay Rieng University in order to improve this research and add insight to readers

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